

Synthesis, spectral, thermal, electrochemical and antibacterial studies of oxomolybdenum(v) and dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes with 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)pyrazol-5-one

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Manuscript received 12 October 2006, revised 6 February 2007, accepted 8 February 2007

Abstract : The Schiff base 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)pyrazol-5-one (AAPCSAL) was prepared by reacting 4-amino antipyrine with 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and a series of metal complexes with this ligand were synthesised by reaction with oxomolybdenum(v) and dioxomolybdenum(vi) having the compositions $[\text{MoOLCl}_2]$, $[\text{MoOL}(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{MoOL}(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{MoOL}(\text{ClO}_4)\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{MoO}_2\text{LCl}]$, $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}(\text{NCS})]$, $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}(\text{NO}_3)]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2\text{L}(\text{ClO}_4)]$ ($\text{L} = \text{AAPCSAL}$). The complexes were characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility data, UV-visible, IR, ESR and NMR spectral studies. NMR and Infrared spectral data suggest that the ligand behaves as a monobasic tridentate chelating agent with ONO donor sequence towards the metal ion. X-Ray diffraction studies of complexes indicated orthorhombic crystal lattice with $a = 7.2785 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.4815 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 14.5569 \text{ \AA}$. The ESR spectral data show that the metal-ligand bond has considerable covalent character. The electrochemical behaviour of the complex was investigated by cyclic voltammetry. The thermal properties of the complexes were investigated by thermogravimetric techniques. The ligand and the complexes have been screened for their antibacterial activities against gram positive and gram negative bacteria.

Keywords : Oxomolybdenum(v), dioxomolybdenum(vi), Schiff base, thermogravimetry.

In view of the importance of oxomolybdenum(v) and dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes, we have prepared and characterized a few new oxomolybdenum(v) and dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes of potential multidentate Schiff base ligand, 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)pyrazol-5-one (AAPCSAL)¹.

AAPCSAL

Results and discussion

All the complexes are deeply coloured, non-hygroscopic, stable crystalline solids. They are soluble in hot nitrobenzene and acetonitrile and sparingly soluble in other common organic solvents. The molar conductance data (Table 1) show that all

the complexes are non-electrolytes². The magnetic moments (Table 1) of Mo^{V} complexes are in the range 1.63–1.83 B.M. which correspond to the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) expected for $\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}\text{O}$ complexes showing the absence of any Mo–Mo interaction. All the dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected for a d^0 -system.

The infrared spectrum of the free ligand exhibited a broad medium intensity band around 3443 cm^{-1} , due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH group. A very strong band occurring at 1645 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is attributed to $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{O})}$ of pyrazolone ring. Another band observed at 1589 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be attributed to the vibrational stretching of azomethine $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{N})}$ group.

The IR spectra of the complexes showed no absorption in the region $3500\text{--}3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating thereby that phenolic group involved in coordination³. The $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{O})}$ phenolic modes of the ligand appearing in the region around 1274 cm^{-1} are shifted to higher frequency in the complexes indicating complex formation via deprotonation of phenolic OH⁴. Thus the $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{O})}$ and $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{N})}$ observed around 1645 and 1589 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum are shifted to ~ 1600 and $\sim 1570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the molybdenum complexes

Complex	Colour	% Mo (Calcd.)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$	CH_3CN	CH_3OH	
$\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2$	Brownish black	18.03 (18.33)	4.8	7.3	13.5	1.63
$\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}$	Yellowish brown	17.00 (17.57)	3.5	25.8	3.5	1.83
$\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})(\text{NO}_3)\text{Cl}$	Yellowish brown	17.53 (17.45)	3.9	30.5	17.4	1.81
$\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})(\text{ClO}_4)\text{Cl}$	Dark brown	15.95 (16.33)	9.5	20.3	10.8	1.67
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}$	Brownish black	18.78 (19.04)	8.7	12.6	4.6	Dia- magnetic
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})(\text{NCS})$	Brown	18.05 (18.24)	4.1	18.7	2.5	Dia- magnetic
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})(\text{NO}_3)$	Yellowish brown	17.85 (18.10)	5.6	23.5	5.8	Dia- magnetic
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})(\text{ClO}_4)$	Dark brown	17.50 (16.90)	6.9	25.5	5.2	Dia- magnetic

All complexes gave satisfactory C, H, N and anion analyses.

the spectra of the complexes, suggesting the participation of these groups in coordination. Thus the ligand AAPCSAL acts as a monobasic tridentate chelating agent in all the complexes.

A very strong band $\sim 960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the oxomolybdenum(V) complexes can be assigned to $\nu_{(\text{Mo}=\text{O})}$ stretching frequency³. Strong bands exhibited by the dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes in the region 947–966 and 910–937 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu_{\text{sym}} \text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}} (\text{O}=\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ respectively of *cis*- MoO_2 moiety⁵. MoO_2 prefers to form a *cis* configuration due to maximum utilization of the available $d\pi$ orbitals for bonding with the oxogroups. The weak bands observed around 570 cm^{-1} in the spectra of these complexes can be attributed to $\nu_{(\text{Mo}-\text{N})}$ where as bands around 420 cm^{-1} can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{O}}$.

The *N*-coordinated nature of the thiocyanate group is indicated by the $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}}$ ($\sim 2040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ ($\sim 760 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and δ NCS ($\sim 480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The IR spectra of the nitrate complexes are suggestive of coordinated nitrate group ($\nu_4 \sim 1490$, $\nu_1 \sim 1340$ and $\nu_2 \sim 1020 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)⁶. For perchlorate complexes, ν_3 and ν_4 appear as strong and medium intensity bands ~ 630 and $\sim 1180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of the ligand displays two sharp singlets which correspond to the methyl protons. $>\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ group of pyrazolone ring appears as a sharp singlet in the region δ (2.18–2.77). Another sharp singlet in the region δ (2.85–3.74) corresponds to the proton of $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$ group. The aromatic rings give a group of multisignals at δ (6.85–7.75). The $\text{CH}=\text{N}$ hydrogen resonates at δ (9.72–9.83) as a sharp

singlet. The ligand shows a peak at δ (13.06–13.21), characteristic of intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH proton. On analysing the spectrum of the complex there is no signal in the region δ (13.06–13.21), thus it can be concluded that the -OH group coordinates to the metal with deprotonation. The IR spectral data are also in conformity with these observations⁴.

Mo^{V} complexes usually exhibit three distinct absorption bands in the region 13500–14500, 19000–22000 and 22500–26000 cm^{-1} , assignable to the transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$). Usually the third band is obscured by the more intense charge transfer transition. $\text{O}(\pi) \rightarrow d(\text{Mo})$ involving the excitation of an electron from the highest filled π -bonding MO (associated mainly with oxygen) to the d -orbitals of Mo. All the present Mo^{V} complexes show bands in the region 13157–15385, 19231–22222 and 25641–27778 cm^{-1} indicating an octahedral geometry. No bands are observed below 10000 cm^{-1} and hence the possibility of a tetrahedral structure can be ruled out. The complexes can be best considered as octahedral with strong tetragonal distortion (C_{4v} symmetry) resulting from the $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ multiple bond.

The ESR spectrum of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$ recorded in polycrystalline form at room temperature, exhibited a single line only. The ESR parameters were found to be $g_{\parallel} = 1.9576$, $g_{\perp} = 1.9264$ and $g_{\text{av}} = 1.9369$. The g_{av} value indicates that the pentavalent Mo in the complex is monomeric⁷.

The cyclic voltammetric study of the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$ was carried out in deaerated acetonitrile in the potential range -2.0 to $+2.0$ V at a scan rate of 100 mV/s. All the complexes show a quasi-reversible peak around -1000 mV (Fig. 1). This can be attributed to the $\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}$ redox system. The electrochemical process is diffusion controlled and decomplexation and metal deposition is not involved⁸.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$

X-Ray powder diffraction patterns of complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$ were examined. The main peaks have been indexed and the d_{hkl} values compared with the calculated ones using Hesse and Lipson's procedure⁹. The observed values fit well with orthorhombic system. The lattice constants for the complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$ were found to be $A = 0.0112$, $B = 0.0066$ and $C = 0.0028$ and unit cell dimensions $a = 7.2785$ Å, $b = 9.4815$ Å and $c = 14.5569$ Å.

The ligand (AAPCSAL) and the complexes $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}]$ were screened for their possible antibacterial activity against gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and the gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 by disc diffusion method¹⁰ at different concentrations using gentamicin as positive control and absolute methanol as negative control. The test results show that the ligand AAPCSAL showed antimicrobial activity against gram positive *S. aureus* at higher concentration of 800 µg per disc giving a zone of inhibition of 1 mm but showed no antimicrobial activity against gram negative *E. coli*. But the complexes $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}]$ did not possess any antimicrobial property against both the gram positive *S. aureus* and gram negative *E. coli*, at the concentration tested.

Thermal behaviour of complexes $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}]$ were studied by TGA in air at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in conjunction with DTG.

The complex $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$ undergoes a two

stage decomposition as indicated by the DTG peaks at 340° and 520° (Fig. 2). A plateau up to 340° in the TG curve indicates that the complex is stable up to this temperature and the absence of coordinated water or other solvent molecules. Weight loss in the first stage (340°) corresponds to the quantitative elimination of two chlorine atoms, and the second stage (520 – 622°) shows the decomposition of the complex to MoO_3 . The final mass loss observed agrees with the values calculated for the conversion of the complex to its oxide (MoO_3).

Fig. 2. TG and DTG curves of $[\text{MoO}(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}_2]$.

The complex $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{AAPCSAL})\text{Cl}]$ decomposed in three well-defined stages leaving a final residue approximating to MoO_3 as reported earlier¹¹. The quantitative elimination of one chlorine atom from the complex occurred in the first stage at 298° . In the second stage (430 – 475°) the quantitative elimination of the ligand took place and at (500 – 650°), complete decomposition of the complex to MoO_3 occurred.

On the basis of the above physicochemical studies, a distorted octahedral geometry is tentatively suggested for the complexes.

(X = Cl, NCS, NO, or ClO_4)
Oxomolybdenum(v) complex

Experimental

MoCl_5 (Aldrich Chemicals, USA), 4-aminoantipyrine (Fluka, Switzerland), 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (Alfa Aesar, Lancaster) and MoO_3 (Lobo Chemie, Bombay) were used as such. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The Schiff

base was prepared by mixing equimolar solutions of 5-chloro salicylaldehyde with 4-aminoantipyrine in methanol and refluxing the reaction mixture on a water bath for *ca.* 1–2 h. On cooling, bright yellow crystals of AAPCSAL were obtained. The crystals were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from hot methanol and dried *in vacuo* at ambient temperature. The purity was tested by TLC elemental analyses, m.p. determination and IR spectra and was also characterized by NMR spectral data.

Oxomolybdenum(v) complexes: The chloride complex was prepared by adding a methanolic solution of MoCl_5 (2 mmol) to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) with vigorous stirring. The dark brown solution which formed was heated over a water bath at 60–65 °C for 10 min. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo*.

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of the thiocyanate, nitrate and perchlorate complexes. By adding a methanolic solution of MoCl_5 (2 mmol) containing ~0.5 g of NH_4CNS or ~0.5 g of LiNO_3 or 3–4 drops of perchloric acid as the case may be, to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol) with vigorous stirring. The resulting solution was heated over a water bath for 5–10 min. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed several times with aqueous methanol and then dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo*.

Dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes: These complexes were prepared in the same manner as the oxomolybdenum(v) complexes. The general method adopted for the preparation of the thiocyanate, nitrate and perchlorate complexes was also the same.

Metal, chloride and sulphur were estimated by standard methods¹². Elemental analyses were carried out at Sophisticated Test and Instrumentation Centre, Kochi. The IR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra of the complexes in methanol were recorded on a Hitachi 220A spectrophotometer. The conductance value of the complexes in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol (*ca.* 10^{-3} M) were measured using an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge with a dip-type cell, fitted with Pt-electrodes. ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded in CDCl_3 on a 300 MHz FT NMR instrument, using TMS as reference. Cyclic voltammetric profile of the complexes were run on a BAS-CV-50W-voltammetric analyzer using glassy carbon as the working electrode. ESR spectra of some complexes were run on a Varian E-112X-Q band spectrometer with DPPH as a

reference material. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of the complexes were recorded using Philips X-Ray PW 1710 diffractometer. The magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature were measured on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections for various atoms and structural units were computed using Pascal's constants. Antibacterial nature of the ligand and the complexes were tested by agar diffusion method.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to RRL, Thiruvananthapuram; STIC, Kochi; IIT Chennai; Sree Chitra Thirunal Institute of Medical Sciences and Technology, Thiruvananthapuram for the facilities. One of us (AS) thanks UGC, New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher fellowship under FIP.

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